

EBFMC25-OOP-23 · Relationship Between Inflammatory Markers and Nutritional Status in Patients Admitted to the Palliative Care Center

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In the presence of malnutrition, it becomes more difficult to fight diseases, and compliance with treatment decreases. In our study, neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR), platelet/lymphocyte ratio (PLR), mean platelet volume (MPV) of patients hospitalized with various diagnoses will be calculated and whether there is a relationship between inflammation and nutrition will be investigated. Patients were screened with NRS-2002 (Nutritional Risk Score) to investigate their nutritional status.

Materials and Methods: The data of 148 patients hospitalized with various diagnoses in the Palliative Care Center Clinic of Tuzla State Hospital between 01.06.2024 - 01.09.2024 were retrospectively scanned. Age, gender, comorbid diseases, feeding type (oral, nasogastric, gastrostomy, parenteral), NRS-2002, BMI (Body Mass Index), Hemogram, Albumin values of the included patients were recorded.

Results: Of the patients included in the study, 52% were male; mean age was 75,27; mean NRS-2002 was 3,11; mean albumin was 2,93; mean Hemoglobin was 10,08. A statistically significant difference was found between malnutrition and NLR. There was no significant difference between the malnutrition risk of those fed enterally and parenterally. A statistically significant difference was found between gender and MPV. No significant relationship was found between hypoalbuminemia, anemia and inflammation markers. A statistically significant difference was found between malnutrition risk and NLR. When we compared comorbid diseases with inflammation markers; A statistically significant relationship was found between malignancy and NLR and between chronic ischemic heart diseases and MPV. A moderately strong and positive correlation was found between NLR and PLR ($p < 0,001$). When we compared the feeding type of the patients with inflammation markers: PLR values of those fed orally and those fed with nasogastric tube, NLR values of those fed orally and those fed parenterally, PLR values of those fed with nasogastric tube and those fed parenterally, NLR values of those fed with nasogastric tube and parenterally fed, there was a statistically significant relationship. A statistically significant difference was found between NRS-2002 and MPV, NLR and PLR values. NLR, PLR, MPV values of those at risk of malnutrition were found to be lower. A negative correlation was found between NRS-2002 and NLR and MPV.

Conclusion: In our study, a statistically significant relationship was observed between malnutrition and inflammation. A statistically significant relationship was observed between the type of nutrition of patients and inflammation. In a study conducted by Rehcinski et al., it was shown that high MPV value is an independent risk factor for myocardial infarction (Rehcinski et al., 2013). Similarly, in our study, a significant relationship was found between MPV and chronic ischemic heart diseases. NLR, which was found to be related to malignancy in our study, is considered to be a predictor of poor prognosis in many cancers (Gu et al., 2015).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Inflammation, palliative care, malnutrition

INTRODUCTION

Palliative care is a multidisciplinary care model aimed at preventing or alleviating potential symptoms in individuals with serious illnesses, seeking to achieve the best quality of life (Morrison & Meier, 2004). Malnutrition can be defined as a decrease in physical and mental functions and a worsening of clinical outcomes caused by deficiencies or irregularities in intake that lead to the deterioration of body composition and body cell mass. The presence of malnutrition complicates the fight against diseases and reduces compliance with treatment. It is known that malnutrition affects mortality, length of hospital stays, and response to treatment, especially in critically ill patients such as those in palliative care. Pro-inflammatory markers such as neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR), platelet/lymphocyte ratio (PLR), and mean platelet volume (MPV) have increasingly been used in recent years (Aksu et al., 2016; Avci et al., 2017; Zahorec, 2021). The physiological response of leukocytes to systemic inflammation involves an increase in neutrophil count and a decrease in lymphocyte count. With the replacement of acute inflammation with chronic inflammation, a decrease in neutrophil count and expected increases in macrophage, lymphocyte, and plasma cell counts occur. NLR is expected to be high in acute inflammation and low in chronic inflammation. Its reflection of these multiple responses, combining neutrophils and lymphocytes that play roles in both acute and chronic inflammatory processes, makes NLR a beneficial indicator of inflammatory response. Studies have shown that tumor cells can gather neutrophils in the tumor stroma via specific chemokines. Subsequently, neutrophils inhibit apoptosis, promote angiogenesis, and metastasis, displaying pro-tumorigenic effects. Infiltrating lymphocytes, which play a role in tumor defense, are associated with a favorable prognosis. NLR reflects the dynamic relationship between innate (neutrophils) and adaptive cellular immune responses (lymphocytes) during disease and various pathological conditions. The normal range for NLR is between 1 and 2; values above 3.0 in adults and below 0.7 are considered pathological. The gray zone for NLR, between 2.3 and 3.0, can serve as an early warning for pathological conditions or processes such as cancer, atherosclerosis, infection, inflammation, psychiatric disorders, and stress (Zahorec, 2021). Studies suggest that NLR could be a prognostic factor in cardiovascular diseases, autoimmune and inflammatory diseases, cancers, and many other disorders. Platelets differ according to their density and size. Mean platelet volume (MPV) is one of the indicators of platelet function. When there is an increase in platelet production, MPV also increases. A platelet volume above 10 femtoliters indicates increased platelet size, while below 6 femtoliters indicates decreased platelet size. Larger than normal volume platelets have been shown to be more reactive and are important markers in predicting atherosclerosis, including coronary artery disease. Many studies suggest that MPV could serve as a prognostic factor in patients with cardiovascular diseases. The platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR), determined by dividing platelet count by lymphocyte count, is believed to be a potentially useful prognostic biomarker in predicting inflammation and mortality. Activated platelets release pro-inflammatory chemokines and cytokines, mediating inflammation. As a new inflammatory marker, PLR is thought to be used as a marker of inflammation and poor prognosis in malignancies, obstructive peripheral artery diseases, atherothrombosis, and atherosclerosis. In our study, we will investigate whether there is a relationship between inflammation and nutrition by calculating the neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR), platelet/lymphocyte ratio (PLR), and mean platelet volume (MPV) of patients admitted with various diagnoses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For this study, ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific Research Ethics Committee of Sehit Prof. Dr. İlhan Varank Education and Research Hospital, numbered 2024/283, on September 12, 2024. Data from 148 patients admitted to the Palliative Care Center Clinic of Tuzla State Hospital between June 1, 2024, and September 1, 2024, were retrospectively reviewed. Recorded data included patients' age, sex, comorbid diseases, type of nutrition (oral, nasogastric, gastrostomy, parenteral), NRS-2002 (Nutritional Risk Score), BMI (Body Mass Index), hemogram, and albumin levels for comparison. Patients were screened using NRS-2002, with a score of 3 or higher considered at risk for malnutrition.

RESULTS

Of the patients included in the study, 52% (n=77) were male; the average age was 75.27; the average BMI was 23.38; the average NRS-2002 score was 3.11; the average albumin was 2.93; the average hemoglobin was 10.08; the average NLR was 5.17; the average PLR was 229.25; and the average MPV was 10.02. While 47.29% of the patients were fed via nasogastric tube, 20.94% via gastrostomy, and 22.29% orally.

Hypoalbuminemia was present in 79.05% of the patients, and anemia was present in 79.72%. It was observed that 64.18% of the patients were at risk for malnutrition. A significant statistical difference was observed between malnutrition and NLR ($p=0.022$). No significant difference was found between the malnutrition risks of enterally and parenterally fed patients. A statistically significant difference was found between sex and MPV ($p=0.013$). No significant relationship was observed between hypoalbuminemia, anemia, and inflammatory markers. When comparing the patients' nutritional types with their albumin levels, a statistically significant difference was found ($p=0.036$). A statistically significant difference was found between malnutrition risk and NLR ($p=0.022$). When comparing the NRS-2002 scores of those fed orally and via nasogastric tube, a statistically significant relationship was observed ($p=0.002$). There was a statistically significant relationship between malignancy and albumin level ($p=0.022$). When comparing comorbid diseases with inflammatory markers, a statistically significant relationship was found between malignancy and NLR ($p<0.05$). A statistically significant relationship was found between chronic ischemic heart diseases and MPV ($p<0.05$). A moderate positive correlation was found between NLR and PLR ($p<0.001$). When comparing the patients' nutritional type with inflammatory markers, a statistically significant relationship was observed between the PLR values of those fed orally and via nasogastric tube ($p<0.05$). A statistically significant relationship was found between the NLR values of those fed orally and parenterally ($p<0.05$). A statistically significant relationship was observed between PLR values of those fed via nasogastric tube and parenteral feeding ($p<0.05$). There was also a statistically significant relationship between the NLR values of those fed via nasogastric tube and parenteral feeding ($p<0.05$). Therefore, we can say that there is a significant relationship between the patients' type of nutrition and inflammatory markers. A statistically significant difference was found between NRS-2002 and MPV, NLR, and PLR ($p<0.05$). The NLR, PLR, and MPV values of those at risk for malnutrition were found to be lower. A negative correlation was found between NRS-2002 and NLR and MPV.

DISCUSSION

In a study conducted by Rehcinski et al., it was shown that high MPV values are an independent risk factor for myocardial infarction (Rehcński et al., 2013). Similarly, in our study, a significant relationship was found between MPV and chronic ischemic heart diseases. Moreover, the observed relationship of NLR with malignancy suggests that it could be a predictor of poor prognosis in many cancers (Gu et al., 2015).

CONCLUSION

In our study, a statistically significant relationship between malnutrition and inflammation was observed. Considering the relationship between malnutrition and inflammation, it should be assessed whether patients under acute or chronic inflammation are at risk for malnutrition, and necessary measures should be taken regarding nutrition. When comparing inflammatory markers with comorbid diseases, a significant relationship was found between MPV and chronic ischemic heart diseases, and NLR and malignancy. Although a significant relationship was observed in this study, research on the correlation between malnutrition and NLR is limited. It was found that there was no difference in malnutrition between enteral and parenteral feeding. The relationship between the patients' nutritional type and inflammatory status is interesting and requires further comparison and investigation in other studies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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